

Online Platforms Utilisation by Academic Staff for Research Visibility in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria: An Inter-disciplinary Approach

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Abstract

Purpose/Aims: The study investigated the use of online platforms, including Google Scholar, Scopus, ResearchGate, and ORCID, for visibility research among scholars in tertiary institutions.

Methodology: The study employed a quantitative approach, administering a questionnaire to collect data from 439 academic staff across disciplines at 6 tertiary institutions in the South-South, Nigeria.

Findings: The study found that academic staff at the institutions studied are aware of some research visibility platforms, such as Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Scopus, and Academia.edu, but are not aware of others, such as ORCID, Kudos, and LinkedIn, for publicising their research papers. The results show that the academic staff studied have created profiles on some visibility platforms, such as ResearchGate, Google Scholar, and Academia.edu, but not on others, such as ORCID, Kudos, Scopus, and LinkedIn. The results show that the academic staff strongly agree and agree that being too busy to create profiles, having no active institutional email, lacking skills to create profiles on these platforms, lacking institutional motivation, facing network challenges, and lacking knowledge about internationally visible journals are drawbacks associated with creating profiles on research visibility platforms.

Conclusion: This study concludes that scholars in tertiary institutions should establish online profiles and link their publications to these platforms. These platforms will undoubtedly enhance academic evaluation and confer greater weight on publications that are accessible globally. The findings of this paper will inform policymakers, administrators, and the management of various tertiary institutions in Nigeria to formulate and make creating profiles on these platforms a mandatory priority.

Keywords: Online Platforms, Research Visibility, Academic Staff, Tertiary Institutions, Nigeria.

Introduction

In today's digital, open-access environments, scholars are discussing the shift in academic norms from "publish or perish" to "get visible or vanish" (Doyle & Cuthill, 2015). Many countries and their educational institutions are increasingly interested in international and national university rankings (Anyira & Idubor, 2020). As a result, the number of both international and national rankings is increasing, and more and more conferences and roundtables are being held to discuss the results. The better a university's results, the greater its chances of showcasing its research and educational potential to the world (Puzatykh, 2021). These rankings are used by many young people as a guide for choosing an educational institution (either locally or internationally). Information on an author's publications and

citations is available in citation databases such as Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Academia, Scopus, Publons, and many others, revealing how well an author is perceived in the scientific community. It's important for faculty members, researchers, scientists, and academics to know that the World Wide Web (www) has emerged as an information hub for conducting research and scientific investigations and as a platform for communicating research results and scientific findings to the intended audience all over the world, despite geographic location and distance. And as visibility of research has become more and more important to academics, higher institutions of learning, and the international community, the online audience has also become more significant for the researcher (Irenea, 2020).

Interest in ICT and Google Scholar among academic staff has been increasing due to their significant benefits. Visibility, or “impact”, is determined by how avidly published work is received by the academic or scientific community. This is where indexing databases such as Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science come in as useful tools for tracking what peers have validated. Visibility is therefore an indirect means of appraising the quality of publications. According to Ayoub et al. (2019), scholars' publication of work online is not only a tool for scholarly communication but also a reliable means of reaching larger audiences and representing the performance and global visibility of institutions. This global visibility extends to the authors of such scholarly publications. Previous studies have reported that the University of Cape Town, University of Witwatersrand, University of Stellenbosch, University of KwaZulu-Natal, and University of Pretoria are leading African universities in webometric rankings, having consistently been among the best ten in Africa (Kpolovie & Obilor, 2013; Lateef, Ogunkunle, & Adigun, 2016). One major reason is the substantial presence of researchers from these universities on Google Scholar Citations. The global research community's response to the COVID-19 pandemic has been phenomenal. Researchers have collaborated across disciplines and regions, shared research outputs rapidly through preprint servers and open platforms, and fast-tracked peer reviews. Meanwhile, publishers have supported this drive by providing free access to content and reducing publication timelines (Torr et al., 2021). Open and rapid sharing of research outputs has undoubtedly helped in the fight against COVID-19.

Generally, Nigerian tertiary institutions have not achieved strong rankings, either globally or in Africa, and several factors have been identified as responsible (Kpolovie & Obilor, 2013). One major factor is that academic staff in Nigerian tertiary institutions publish their research papers in local journals that are not indexed by international indexing and abstracting agencies, resulting in limited visibility. Although Nigeria produces high-quality research, without an audience, the work remains confined to the pages of invisible, low-impact-factor local journals and accumulates on our shelves, gathering dust. There is thus a need for a strategy that considers where we publish and how to find and attract an audience for our publications, thereby helping academic staff create and maintain global visibility. Today, many research dissemination tools, such as Google Scholar, Scopus, LinkedIn, ResearchGate, and Mendeley, are available to researchers, including research reports, peer-reviewed publications, press releases, and policy briefs (World Health Organisation, 2014). Recently, due to the poor ranking of Nigerian universities, the National Universities Commission directed that all academic staff in Nigerian public universities register and create profiles on platforms such as Google Scholar, Scopus, and ORCID. The bottom line remains the creation and maintenance of global visibility for Nigerian scholars in publishing. Therefore, the present study aims to elucidate the extent of use of various research visibility platforms by academic staff in Nigerian tertiary institutions to make their research globally visible. To achieve this, the following research questions were raised to guide the study. They are:

Research Questions

1. How many academic staff in tertiary institutions are aware of the research visibility platforms?
2. To what extent have academic staff in the tertiary institutions created profiles in the research visibility platforms?
3. To what extent are academic staff in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria aware of the different ways to make their research visible globally?
4. What are the drawbacks associated with creating profiles with the research visibility platforms?

Literature Review

Today, traditional libraries have given way to new channels, previously unthinkable, for the dissemination and knowledge of scientific research results, such as common social networks, scientific social networks (specifically designed for this purpose and for the exclusive use of the research community), audiovisual channels (such as YouTube, Vimeo and others), and institutional repositories. These channels offer a wide range of possibilities for research to move and become visible beyond physical boundaries (Aguaded, 2021). Research visibility is essential for opportunistic/pragmatic reasons, such as self-promotion for recognition and reputation, employment/appointment; for gaining competitive advantage over peers in terms of, for example, recruitment and attraction of better staff or students and outperforming others; enabling and fostering transparency and accessibility to resources and research output; gaining credibility and respect from peers or competitors and stakeholders; supporting research development or capacity building and knowledge sharing; enabling access to information for benchmarking, for example, for university rankings; supporting scholarly communication; and attracting funding/sponsors/support (Ocholla, Mostert & Rotich, 2016).

Some Online Visibility Platforms utilised by Academics

ORCID

It has been proposed that implementing an author identification system such as ORCID could significantly aid in consolidating all authors' contributions to knowledge, providing a comprehensive record of individual scholarly work (Akidi, Osedo & Chukwueke, 2021). As the use of ORCID becomes more commonplace, funding organisations are expected to require ORCID identifiers in grant applications. They plan to utilise these IDs to streamline and simplify the grant submission procedure, reducing administrative burden. Similarly, publishers now commonly request research identifiers, such as ORCID, during manuscript submission to ensure that the work is accurately attributed to its creator, safeguarding authorship and recognition (Akidi, Osedo & Chukwueke, 2021). Your ORCID iD will serve as a lifelong, persistent identifier that remains with you throughout your scholarly career. It will help distinguish you from other researchers and guarantee consistent, reliable attribution of your works, thereby enhancing your professional reputation and ensuring you receive proper credit for your contributions.

Google Scholar

Creating a public Google Scholar profile is an easy way to increase your findability and provides other benefits such as an author H-index, citation counts, and more. Google Scholar (GS) (<http://scholar.google.com>), launched on November 18, 2004 (Jacso, 2005), is a database of full-text journal articles, technical reports, conference proceedings, preprints, theses, books, and other documents, including selected Web pages deemed scholarly or academic. These resources are freely available, and even for subscription-based publications, searches yield at least an abstract of the article.

GS has enjoyed patronage and a commendable presence on college and university websites (Neuhaus, Neuhaus & Asher, 2008), indicating the degree of its adoption. Its coverage across a wide set of disciplines has been increasing at a stable rate (Harzing, 2014), indicating its suitability for research evaluation and bibliometric research purposes, more so than in the past.

Scopus

Founded by Elsevier in 2004, Scopus has rapidly expanded to become one of the largest and most comprehensive index and citation databases of peer-reviewed literature. It encompasses a wide range of scientific journals, books, and conference proceedings across numerous disciplines, including emerging and interdisciplinary fields (Schotten et al., 2017). The database offers extensive global and regional coverage, including content from over 39,100 serial titles—recently indexed from more than 24,500 of these—as well as 120,000 conferences and 206,000 books published by more than 5,000 publishers worldwide (www.scopus.com). As a curated resource, Scopus maintains high standards for content quality and relevance through a rigorous selection process overseen by an independent Content Selection and Advisory Board (Baas et al., 2020), which continually reviews and updates its criteria to reflect evolving scientific standards and publication practices.

ResearchGate.net

ResearchGate (RG) is the largest professional network for scientists; it enables researchers to connect with colleagues, build their scientific networks, and collaborate using numerous applications unique to the scientific platform. RG has nearly doubled its population in one year. It was founded in 2008, and it has more than 16 million users, over 200 million publications and over 53 million monthly visits (Source: www.researchgate.net/about). Every publication within ResearchGate's Literature is accompanied by a series of details and interactive features. The author's and the reader's profiles are linked to the publication. Researchers can post comments or queries and share the article within their network. A list of similar publications is also provided, facilitating researchers' discovery of related literature. ResearchGate's "About" page states, "Our mission is to connect researchers and make it easy for them to share and access scientific output, knowledge, and expertise (Source: www.researchgate.net/about).

These tools and many others provide comprehensive visibility into researchers' scientific production and impact, serving as key resources for understanding their curricula in terms of volume and community impact (measured by citations), as well as the progression of their academic life cycle. Recently, it has become more common for universities to recognize only research published in prestigious, indexed, and abstracted journals in Nigeria. These requirements arise because indices provide specific metrics that rank journal success and each author's citation impact. High ratings help authors and their affiliated universities gain recognition in the academic community and access greater research funding, which in turn allows their careers and programs to flourish (Elisha, 2019). The importance of scholars' web presence, including homepages, LinkedIn, Google Scholar citations, and Twitter accounts, has been studied in previous work to establish visibility (Bar-Ilan et al., 2012). Ranking authorities do not visit universities physically; their web presence is what counts. This implies that an institution may have the highest number of quality academics coupled with robust infrastructure, publish regularly and adequately in print and non-open access journals, but if its web presence is limited, the ranking will be very low (Elisha, 2019; Lateef, Ogunkunle & Adigun, 2016). Ranking authorities are only interested in how you communicate these achievements to people all over the world and, more so, the impacts of your achievements on people's lives (Elisha, 2019). The Nigerian Universities Commission (2006) pinpointed the following as factors responsible for Nigerian universities' poor

performance in international rankings: i. little attention is paid to communicating research findings conducted by scholars in Nigerian universities in a web-searchable form, which manifests in publishing in low-impact local journals without Internet links and in not publishing in electronic journals, especially open access journals; ii. absence of Nigerian universities on the Internet in a form that can be picked up by the radar of webometrics and allied organisations; iii. lack of up-to-date and scanty content on the websites of Nigerian universities.

In analysing the visibility criteria, Puzatykh (2021) reported on Bunin Yelets State University (BYSU) in Russia and found only 3 profiles that included the university's full name. The author added that the system requires employees to have email addresses associated with the university's official domain. Akidi, Osedo and Chukwueke (2021) reported that maintaining publishing standards and global visibility require calculated steps and efforts, including producing a scholarly article and publishing it in high-impact online scientific journals. The authors added that conducting high-quality research produces high-quality journal articles that increase visibility. Anyira and Idubor (2020) recommended that one solution to poor webometrics ranking is to improve scholarly/research endeavors, which include: mandating all academic staff to publish a minimum of three articles yearly in highly rated open access journals in their fields; registering all teaching staff on Google Scholar and ResearchGate platforms; making it compulsory for all staff publications and students' projects/theses/dissertations to be in the institution's open access repository; and encouraging all scholars to place all their publications (pre-prints and post-prints) on their web domains. The study by Ocholla, Mostert, and Rotich (2016) compared the visibility of researchers from the University of Zululand and Moi University in Web of Science and Scopus from 2003 to 2013 and found significant differences in the output of the two universities when considering the top twenty researchers with visible research publications. Moi University had a higher mean in the fields considered, except in the total records of WoS, where the University of Zululand had a mean of 19.80, and Moi had a mean of 15.60. A search of Scopus and Web of Science for researchers from the two institutions during the research period revealed a significant difference in visibility. The mean across all fields was higher in Scopus, indicating that the database captures more research output. Ocholla, Mostert, and Rotich (2016) recommended that researchers be encouraged to publish more in internationally visible research outlets/publications that are widely indexed in Scopus or Thomson Reuters Web of Science, or both, to demonstrate and account for research quality and increase research visibility.

Bar-Ilan et al. (2012) examined the importance of scholars' web presence, including homepages, profiles on platforms such as LinkedIn, Google Scholar citations, and Twitter accounts, to establish visibility. The study found that web presence was widespread and diverse: 84% of scholars had homepages, 70% were on LinkedIn, 23% had public Google Scholar profiles, and 16% were on Twitter. Lateef, Ogunkunle, and Adigun (2016) suggested that the rankings of several public universities in Nigeria would have been higher if their academic communities had an impressive online presence, including Google Scholar citation profiles. The authors noted that the low value of fewer than 100 registered users among first- and second-generation universities established in the past 4-6 decades indicated a low level of scholars' web presence. Torr et al. (2021) conducted a study of 1,500 academic researchers from Emerald's Literati database, with respondents from over 100 countries worldwide. The survey asked academics how information and research should be presented to further real-world impact and found that academics preferred more open content (43%), greater accessibility (43%), and metrics that demonstrate real-world impact (41%). The impact of the research is measured and analyzed through citation analysis. The number of citations suggests the quality of the scientific information. Google Scholar, a freely available scientometric database, indexes academic papers from open-access repositories and commercial sources and also identifies cited references.

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design. A questionnaire was designed to collect quantitative data from academic staff across disciplines in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The study covered academic staff in colleges of education, polytechnics, and universities in the South-South region of Nigeria. The questionnaire was distributed to academic staff across disciplines. A convenient sampling technique was used to distribute the questionnaires to respondents. Data collection began in July 2024 and ended in February 2025. In total, 439 academic staff in colleges of education, polytechnics, and universities in the South-South region of Nigeria responded to the survey. A breakdown of respondents by institution and number is shown in Table 1. The collected data were analysed, and the results were presented in charts and tables.

Results

Table 1: Number of respondents according to institution.

s/n	Institution	Type of institution	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Isaac Jasper Boro College of Education, Sagbama, Bayelsa State.	College of Education	57	13.0%
2	College of Education, Warri.	College of Education.	63	14.3%
3	Federal Polytechnic Ekowe, Bayelsa State.	Polytechnic	49	11.2%
4	Delta State Polytechnic, Otefe-Oghara, Delta State.	Polytechnic	71	16.2%
5	Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Amassoma.	University	92	21.0%
6	Delta State University, Abraka.	University	107	24.3%
Total			439	100%

Of the 439 respondents, 107 (24.3%) identified as staff of Delta State University, Abraka, the highest, followed by 92 (21.0%) who identified as staff of Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Amassoma, and 71 (16.2%) who identified as staff of Delta State Polytechnic, Otefe-Oghara, Delta State (see details in Table 1).

Staff position/rank

For the purpose of this study, the staff position/rank is placed into two broad categories:

(1) Junior academic staff = Assistant librarian/Graduate assistant– Librarian II/ Lecturer II.

(2) Senior academic staff = Senior librarian/Lecturer I– University Librarian/ Professors.

Out of the 439 respondents, 211(48.1%) are junior academic staff, while more than half (228: 51.9%) are senior academic staff.

Academic staff in tertiary institutions' level of awareness of the research visibility platforms.

Respondents were asked to indicate their awareness of research visibility platforms. The majority reported being aware of Google Scholar (337; 76.8%), the ResearchGate network (401; 91.3%), Scopus (355; 80.9%), and Academia.edu (404; 92.0%). However, they reported being unfamiliar with research visibility platforms such as ORCID (240: 54.7%), Kudos (279: 63.6%), and LinkedIn (289: 65.8%). This shows that the academic staff in the institutions studied are aware of some research visibility

platforms, such as Google Scholar, the ResearchGate network, Scopus, and Academia.edu, but not others, like ORCID, Kudos, and LinkedIn, for publicising their research papers (Table 2).

Table 2: Awareness of visibility platforms

Awareness of visibility platforms	I am aware	Not aware
ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor identifier)	199 (45.3%)	240 (54.7%)
Google Scholar	337 (76.8%)	102 (23.2%)
kudos	160 (36.4%)	279 (63.6%)
ResearchGate network	401 (91.3%)	38 (8.7%)
Scopus	355 (80.9%)	84 (19.1%)
LinkedIn	150 (34.2%)	289 (65.8%)
Academia.edu	404 (92.0%)	35 (8.0%)

Extent of creating profiles in the research visibility platforms by academic staff in the tertiary institutions.

Respondents were asked which of the following visibility platforms they have created profiles on to showcase their intellectual output to the world. They were asked to select all that apply. Of the 439 respondents, 314 (71.5%) indicated that they had created a profile on ResearchGate, the highest number, followed by 281 (64.0%) on Google Scholar and 189 (43.1%) on Academia.edu. Meanwhile, only 171 (39.0%) indicated having a profile on ORCID, 94 (21.4%) on Kudos, 82 (18.7%) on Scopus, and 73 (16.6%) on LinkedIn (Figure 1). The results show that the academic staff studied have created profiles on some visibility platforms, such as ResearchGate, Google Scholar, and Academia.edu, but not on others, such as ORCID, Kudos, Scopus, and LinkedIn.

Figure 1: Visibility Platforms Academic Staff Create Profile

Level of awareness of the different ways to make their research visible globally.

Respondents were asked to indicate their level of awareness of ways to make research visible globally. The majority (321: 73.1%) indicated that they know that publishing open access is a way to make research visible globally. 294 (67.0%) also indicated that communicating your work at national and international conferences is a way to make research visible globally, and 277 (63.1%) indicated that creating a Google Scholar profile, an academia.edu profile, a Kudos profile, and joining the ResearchGate network are ways to make research visible globally.

On the other hand, more than half, 281 (64.0%), indicated that they don't know that one way to make their research visible is to share their data through their school's academic community platform, and 301 (68.5%) also indicated they don't know that one way to make their research visible is to deposit the preprint version of their paper on their website. The findings reveal that academic staff members know that publishing open access, communicating their work at national and international conferences, creating Google Scholar, Academia.edu, and Kudos profiles, and joining the ResearchGate network are ways to make research visible globally. However, the majority indicated that they are not aware that they can share their data through their school's academic community platform and deposit the preprint version of their paper on their website.

Table 3: Awareness of ways of making research visible globally

Ways of making research visible globally	I know	I don't know	I only heard
Select the best journals within your discipline.	65 (14.8%)	170 (38.7%)	204 (46.5%)
Publish Open Access (making your publication OA provides a citation advantage).	321 (73.1%)	39 (8.9%)	79 (18.0%)
Deposit and provide Open Access to your articles on an institutional repository.	218 (49.6%)	107 (24.4%)	114(26.0%)
Share your data through your school academic community platform.	119(27.1%)	281(64.0%)	39(8.9%)
Deposit the preprint version of your paper on your website.	93(21.2%)	301(68.5%)	45(10.3%)
Communicate your work at national/international conferences.	294(67.0%)	118(26.9%)	27(6.1%)
Create an ORCID identifier.	108(24.6%)	244(55.6%)	87 (19.8%)
Create a Google Scholar Profile, a academia.edu profile, kudos profile and join ResearchGate network.	277(63.1%)	129(29.4%)	33(7.5%)
Unambiguously link your publications to your profiles and interconnect all information.	68 (15.5%)	141(32.1%)	230(52.4%)

Drawbacks associated with creating profiles on the research visibility platforms.

Regarding drawbacks associated with creating profiles on research visibility platforms, the majority (296; 67.4%) strongly agree or agree that they are too busy to create their profiles. More than half (225: 51.3%) also strongly agree and agree that they don't have an active institutional email. More than half (257: 58.5%) also strongly agree and agree that they lack the skills to create a profile on these platforms. The majority (292; 66.5%) strongly agree or agree that their institution lacks motivation to make their research visible globally. The majority (320; 72.9%) strongly agree or agree that network challenges are drawbacks associated with creating profiles on research visibility platforms. The majority (315: 71.7%) strongly agree and agree that the inability to conduct high-quality research is not a drawback associated with creating profiles on research visibility platforms. The majority (275: 62.6%) strongly agree and agree that a lack of knowledge about internationally visible journals is a drawback associated with creating profiles on research visibility platforms (Table 4). The results show that the academic

staff strongly agree and agree that being too busy to create a profile, not having an active institutional email, lacking skills to create a profile on these platforms, lacking institutional motivation, facing network challenges, and lacking knowledge about international visible journals are drawbacks associated with creating profiles on research visibility platforms.

Table 4: Drawbacks associated with creating profiles with the research visibility platforms.

Drawbacks	SA	A	D	SA
Too busy to create my profile	191 (43.5%)	105(23.9%)	81(18.5%)	62(14.1%)
No active institutional email	119(27.1%)	106(24.1%)	93(21.2%)	121(27.6%)
Lack of skills on how to create profile on these platforms.	124(28.2%)	133(30.3%)	101(23.0%)	81(18.5%)
Lack of motivation from the institution	202(46.0%)	90(20.5%)	121(27.6%)	26(5.9%)
Network challenges	217(49.4%)	103(23.5%)	95(21.6%)	24(5.5%)
Inability to conduct high-quality research	42(9.6%)	82(18.7%)	212(48.3%)	103(23.4%)
Lack of knowledge about internationally visible journals	166(37.8%)	109(24.8%)	88(20.1%)	76(17.3%)

Discussion of findings

Level of awareness of the research visibility platforms by academic staff in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

The analysis of awareness of research visibility platforms shows that academic staff in the institutions studied are aware of some platforms, such as Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Scopus, and Academia.edu, but not others, like ORCID, Kudos, and LinkedIn, for publicising their research papers. The results indicate that awareness is uneven across platforms. This suggests a need to raise awareness so that all academic staff become familiar with research visibility platforms, including ORCID, Kudos, and LinkedIn. These findings are consistent with those of Baro, Tralagba, and Ebiagbe (2018), who studied knowledge and use of self-archiving options among academic librarians working in universities in Africa and found that they are aware of ResearchGate, institutional repositories, personal websites/servers, Kudos, and Mendeley. Recently, many tertiary institutions in Nigeria have issued memos directing academic staff to create profiles on online visibility platforms to increase the visibility of papers, authors, and the institution. The study by Bosah et al. (2017) revealed that academic librarians at African universities are aware of IRs, ResearchGate, and Academia.edu and use IRs and ResearchGate to self-archive their publications.

Extent of creating profiles in the research visibility platforms by academic staff in the tertiary institutions.

Analysis of profiles on research visibility platforms indicates that the academic staff studied have created profiles on some platforms, such as ResearchGate, Google Scholar, and Academia.edu, but not on others, such as ORCID, Kudos, Scopus, and LinkedIn. This indicates that many academic staff have not yet taken advantage of the benefits of creating profiles on research visibility platforms such as ORCID, Kudos, Scopus, and LinkedIn. This finding is consistent with Baro, Tralagba, and Ebiagbe's (2018).

The overwhelming majority of academic librarians reported using one or two self-archiving options to make their papers accessible globally. Similarly, Doyle & Cuthill (2015) reported that creating a public Google Scholar profile is an easy way to increase your findability and provides other benefits, such as an author H-index, citation counts, and more. If Nigerian or African institutions can implement a

mandatory policy requiring academic staff to create profiles on platforms such as Google Scholar, Scopus, ResearchGate, and others, it will help make their research papers visible globally, thereby creating a web presence that improves ranking positions and, in this way, makes the institutions more attractive to potential entrants. Kpolovie and Obilor (2013) reported that Nigerian universities have not enjoyed good rankings, both in the world and in Africa, and that a number of factors have been found to be responsible, including lack of visibility.

The extent of the academic staff's awareness of the different ways to make their research visible globally.

The findings reveal that academic staff members recognise that publishing open access, presenting work at national and international conferences, creating profiles on Google Scholar, Academia.edu, and Kudos, and joining the ResearchGate network are ways to make research visible globally. This finding aligns with previous studies, such as Torr et al. (2021), which reported numerous benefits of creating public profiles on online visibility platforms. The study, therefore, called for authors to publish more in internationally visible journals that are widely indexed and abstracted. The present study also found that most were unaware that they can share their data through their school's academic community platform and deposit the preprint version of their paper on their website. In line with this finding, Doyle & Cuthill (2015) identified several ways to increase the visibility of research work, including: select the best journals within your discipline, publish Open Access (making your publication OA provides a citation advantage), deposit and provide Open Access to your articles in an institutional repository, create an ORCID identifier, create a Google Scholar Profile, join the ResearchGate network, and create other visibility profiles. Liauw and Genoni (2017) reported that developments in OA have supported an alternative form of scholarly communication that has enabled, to a certain degree, the availability of freely accessible online scholarly content. The study by Hitchcock et al. (2003) found that across all disciplines, the distribution of citation counts indicates that articles in OA have higher citation counts. These distributions also suggest that the greatest impact of OA is on the most-cited articles. Studies have shown that citation counts are widely used in formal and informal research evaluations as indicators of scholarly impact (Thelwall, 2017).

Drawbacks associated with creating profiles on the research visibility platforms.

The results show that academic staff strongly agree and agree that being too busy to create a profile, having an inactive institutional email, lacking skills to create profiles on these platforms, lacking institutional motivation, facing network challenges, and lacking knowledge of internationally visible journals are drawbacks associated with creating profiles on research visibility platforms. To overcome these drawbacks, academic staff in Nigerian tertiary institutions need to allocate time to create profiles and activate their institutional email accounts. In the digital age, academic staff across disciplines need to acquire ICT skills to create profiles on these online visibility platforms. The study by Elisha (2019) identified poor ICT proficiency and a negative attitude toward ICT as challenges for academic staff using Google Scholar accounts. The study suggested that higher education administrators should ensure that academic staff engage in this historic development to position their institution among world-class colleges, in accordance with the institution's vision.

Conclusion

Academic staff in the institutions studied are aware of some research visibility platforms but not others. This calls for sensitisation among academic staff to create profiles on various online platforms and make their research outputs visible globally. The use of these research visibility platforms by academic staff in tertiary institutions will undoubtedly add weight to publications that are accessible globally and make

scholars in tertiary institutions in Nigeria visible worldwide, thereby boosting institutional rankings. Creating academic profiles, especially on open-access platforms, to improve search results and provide access to one's work will increase the online visibility of the paper and the author. In the field of scientific dissemination, the research process does not end with the publication of the work; rather, it is from that moment that a key phase for the life of the work begins: its dissemination and impact. These findings will enable researchers and policymakers to assess developments and trends within the academic community regarding the level of visibility of its institutions and staff.

Based on the findings, the study recommends that institutions, as a matter of policy, require all academic staff to create profiles and upload their intellectual output for global accessibility.

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References

- Aguaded, I. (2021). Visibility and impact of our research: Publons, Scopus and Google Scholar Metrics. <https://doi.org/10.3916/school-of-authors-165>
- Akidi, J., Osedo, O. A. & Chukwueke, C. (2021). Maintaining Publishing Standards and Global Visibility: Essential Tips for Nigerian Library and Information Professionals. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 5554. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5554>
- Anyira, I. E. & Idubor, I. (2020). Poor Webometrics Ranking of Nigerian Higher Institutions: Causes, Implications, and Solutions. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 4200. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4200>
- Ayoub, A., Amin, R., Amin, S., & Wani, Z. A. (2019). Global visibility and web impact of leading universities of SAARC Nations. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 2443. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/2443>
- Baas, J., Schotten, M., Plume, A., Cote, G., & Karimi, R. (2020). Scopus as a curated, high-quality bibliometric data source for academic research in quantitative science studies. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(1), 377–386.
- Bar-Ilan, J., Haustein, S., Peters, I., Priem, J., Shema, H., & Terliesner, J. (2012). Beyond citations: Scholars' visibility on the social Web. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1205.5611*.
- Baro, E. E., Tralagba, E. C., & Ebiagbe, E. J. (2018). Knowledge and use of self-archiving options among academic librarians working in universities in Africa. *Information and Learning Science*, 119 (3/4), 145-160.
- Bosah, G., Okeji, C.C. & Baro, E.E. (2017), "Perceptions, preferences of scholarly publishing in open access journals: a survey of academic librarians in Africa", *Digital Library Perspectives*, 33 (4), 378-394.
- Doyle, J. & Cuthill, M. (2015) Does 'get visible or vanish' herald the end of 'publish or perish'? *Higher Education Research & Development*, 34:3, 671-674
- Elisha, D. (2019). The Need for Google Scholar Account for Academic Staff of Higher Education. *Global scientific journal*, 7 (9), 12–24.
- Harzing, A. W. (2014). A longitudinal study of Google Scholar coverage between 2012 and 2013. *Scientometrics*, 98(1), 565-575.

- Hitchcock, S., Brody, T., Gutteridge, C., Carr, L. & Harnad, S. (2003). The impact of OAI-based search on access to research journal papers. *Serials Review*, 16 (3), <http://opcit.eprints.org/serials-short/serials11.html>
- Jacso, P. (2005). As We May Search: Comparison of Major Features of the Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar Citation-Based and Citation-Enhanced Databases. *Current Science*, 89(9),1537–1547.
- Kpolovie, P. J., & Obilor, I. E. (2013). Nigerian universities bag ludicrous ranks in the world rankings of universities. *Universal Journal of Education and General Studies* 2(9), 303-323.
- Lateef, A., Ogunkunle, A. T. J., & Adigun, G. O. (2016). Google Scholar citation in retrospect: Visibility and contributions of African Scholars, *COLLNET Journal of Scientometrics and Information Management*, 10(2), 219–236.
- Liau, T. & Genoni, P. (2017). A different shade of green: a survey of Indonesian higher education institutional repositories. *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication*, 4 (1), 219–225.
- Neuhaus, C., Neuhaus, E., & Asher, A. (2008). Google Scholar goes to school: The presence of Google Scholar on college and university websites. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 34(1), 39–51.
- Nigerian Universities Commission (NUC) (2006). 2002 ‘webometrics ranking of world universities: matters arising, *NUC Monday Memo*, March 13.
- Ocholla, D. N., Mostert, J. & Rotich, D. C. (2016). Visibility of University of Zululand and Moi University Researchers in Web of Science and Scopus from 2003 to 2013. *African Journal of Library, Archive & Information Science*, 26 (1), 3-15.
- Puzatykh, A. (2021). Webometrics Ranking and Regional Universities: Analyzing Results of Bunin Yelets State University. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2021.12.95>.
- Schotten, M., el Aisati, M., Meester, W. J., Steinginga, S., & Ross, C. A. (2017). A Brief History of Scopus: The world’s largest abstract and citation database of scientific literature. In F. J. Cantú-Ortiz (Ed.), *Research Analytics. Boosting University Productivity and Competitiveness through Scientometrics* (pp. 31–58). Boca Raton, FL: Taylor & Francis Group.
- Thelwall, M. (2017). Why do papers have many Mendeley readers but few Scopus-indexed citations and vice versa?”, *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 49 (2), 144-151.
- Torr, R., Kildunne, A., Johnston-Hughes, T., Sutcliffe, M. & Etchells, L., (2021). Is research output fit for the future? Closing the impact gap. *Emerald Publishing*.<https://www.emeraldgrouppublishing.com/sites/default/files/2021-05/Closing%20the%20imact%20gap%20demographics.pdf>